

Automated Patient Engagement and Tracking for Colorectal Cancer Screening in Primary Care

Version 1

Description

This project addresses critically low uptake of colorectal cancer screening in Latvia. Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer in the world and one of the leading causes of cancer death, so early detection is essential. Automated Patient Engagement and Tracking for Colorectal Cancer Screening in Primary Care (Nr. Izp-2024/1-0454).

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Izp-2024/1-0454

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Stradinš University (RSU)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Automated Patient Engagement and Tracking for Colorectal Cancer Screening in Primary Care

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Izp-2024/1-0454

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-03-11

4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset for FLPP project Izp-2024/1-0454

Data Management Plan for the project "Automated Patient Engagement and Tracking for Colorectal Cancer Screening in Primary Care (Nr. Izp-2024/1-0454)".

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data collection for colorectal cancer (CRC) screening will involve gathering information from the implemented tool on patient invitations, visit attendance, and screening outcomes.

The automated tool, implemented in GP practices, will collect data on colorectal cancer screening, including patient invitations, visit attendance, and screening results.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Aggregated data collected from the automated colorectal cancer screening tool will provide valuable insights into the efficiency of the invitation system. By analyzing metrics such as invitation uptake rates, and screening completion percentages, researchers and government agencies can assess the system's performance. This anonymized, summarized data can inform decisions regarding program optimization, resource allocation, and policy adjustments to improve

screening participation and ultimately contribute to better public health outcomes in colorectal cancer prevention.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Ratings
- Process produced data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- JSON
- Others

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

1 GB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

In the current project scope, there are no plans to re-use other datasets.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI metadata standard

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

ICD-10

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook
- ReadMe file
- Methodology description
- Software documentation

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Currently, our dataset has a relatively simple structure. However, we anticipate that the data structure may evolve as the project progresses and the automated screening tool is further developed. We will document any changes to the file organization, including file naming conventions and directory structure, in our project's ReadMe file and data dictionary, ensuring consistent and clear documentation throughout the project lifecycle.

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data will be provided in CSV and/or JSON formats. Both formats are non-proprietary, ensuring accessibility with widely used and free software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

To access the CSV and JSON data, users can utilize common spreadsheet software, text editors, programming languages like Python or R with relevant libraries, or database management systems.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

Yes

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

While we do not plan to use a formal, domain-specific ontology at this stage, we will ensure interoperability by using clear and consistent terminology within our codebook and documentation, and we will adopt standard field names where applicable, with consideration for potential future alignment with established vocabularies in the healthcare domain.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Riga Stradins University dataverse

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Processing

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU Dataverse long term preservation costs are covered by RSU.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

Rīga Stradiņš University

RSU will manage and handle all data.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Didzis Rutitis (orcid: [0000-0002-9621-6513](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9621-6513))
- Artis Alksnis (0009-0005-3904-0784)

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Specific data quality assurance processes will be defined, updated and documented in detail at a later stage of the project.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Hash functions

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

During the research phase, operational data generated by the automated screening tool will be stored in a secure database located within Europe, ensuring compliance with relevant data privacy regulations. The best long-term storage solution for the extracted data used for analysis will be determined at a later stage, taking into consideration factors such as data volume, sensitivity, and intended use, with a commitment to following FAIR data principles.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Potential limitations (ethical and legal aspects) have been identified, but all of these will be taken into account during data collection, processing, and storage. One example of this is the anonymization of data to protect patient personal data.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

Yes

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

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